

Volar Locked Plate Versus Ligamentotaxis in Fixation of AO Type C Distal Radius Fracture Regarding Functional Outcomes: A Comparative Prospective Study

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Abstract

Background: Type C intra-articular distal radius fractures are complex, and the relative benefits of volar locked plate fixation versus external fixation based on ligament taxis remain debated. Aim of the study: This study compared functional outcomes of these two surgical procedures.

Patients and methods: In a prospective comparative cohort study at a single tertiary center, 45 adults with AO Type C distal radius fractures were treated with external fixation based on ligamentotaxis ($n = 24$) or volar locked plate fixation ($n = 21$). Patients were followed up at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, and 3 months. Functional outcome was recorded at 3 months' post-op and it included pain on a visual analogue scale, wrist and forearm range of motion, grip strength, Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand questionnaire score, complications, and time to return to work.

Results: At 3 months' post-op, Volar locked plate fixation yielded lower pain scores (mean 2.4 vs 3.5; $p < 0.001$), higher grip strength (81.4% vs 75.2%; $p = 0.024$), and earlier return to work (8.1 vs 10.0 weeks; $p = 0.005$) than external fixation. Wrist extension and forearm supination were significantly greater ($p = 0.011$ and $p = 0.006$, respectively) in the Volar locked plate treated group. Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand scores were lower after volar locked plate fixation but not significantly different ($p = 0.2$), and complication rates were low and similar in both groups.

Conclusion: Volar locked plate fixation provided better functional outcomes and earlier return to work than external fixation based on ligament taxis.

More Information

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Keywords:

Distal radius fracture; volar locked plate; external fixation; ligamentotaxis; functional outcome; Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand.

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Introduction

Distal radius fractures (DRFs) are among the most common skeletal injuries encountered in orthopedic practice, accounting for approximately 18% of adult fractures [1]. Their incidence is increasing worldwide, particularly among older adults due to osteoporosis and low-energy falls, while younger individuals often sustain these injuries through high-energy trauma [2,3]. Complete intra-articular fractures classified as AO/OTA type C represent a particularly challenging subgroup because they involve disruption of the radiocarpal joint surface and metaphyseal comminution, increasing the risk of post-traumatic arthritis and functional impairment if anatomical reduction is not achieved [5,6]. Successful management of AO/OTA type C fractures requires restoration of

articular congruity, radial height, inclination, and volar tilt, along with stable fixation that permits early mobilization [7]. The distal radius anatomy—including the scaphoid and lunate fossae, radial styloid, sigmoid notch, and the three-column concept—plays a crucial role in understanding fracture patterns and guiding fixation strategies [8,9]. Special attention must also be given to the volar “watershed” line and surrounding neurovascular and tendon structures to prevent hardware-related complications [9,10]. Two principal operative approaches are commonly employed for unstable intra-articular fractures: volar locked plate (VLP) fixation and external fixation using ligamentotaxis (EF). VLP fixation provides angular stability through locking screw technology, facilitating anatomical reduction and allowing early wrist motion. Randomized

trials and meta-analyses demonstrate superior early functional recovery—particularly improved grip strength and range of motion—within the first postoperative months, although long-term differences compared with EF often diminish by one year [11,12]. Advances in plate design and biomechanics have further enhanced subchondral support and reduced hardware-related complications [13,14]. Conversely, ligamentotaxis via external fixation relies on controlled distraction to realign fracture fragments indirectly through intact soft tissues. This minimally invasive technique preserves the soft-tissue envelope and can be particularly useful in severely comminuted fractures or when soft-tissue conditions limit open surgery [15,16]. However, EF is associated with complications such as pin-site infection, loss of reduction, and postoperative stiffness, and may provide less precise articular reduction in highly comminuted patterns [17,18]. The aim of study is to compare the functional outcomes of AO/OTA type C intra-articular distal radius fractures treated with volar locked plate (VLP) fixation versus ligamentotaxis using external fixation (EF), and to evaluate associated radiographic results and complication rates between the two techniques.

Method

Study Design and Setting

This prospective cohort study was conducted at Al-Emamain Al-Kadhmain Medical City over a one-year period (1 November 2024 to 1 November 2025) to compare functional outcomes of AO/OTA type C distal radius fractures treated with ligamentotaxis using external fixation (EF) versus volar locked plate (VLP) fixation. A total of 45 adult patients were enrolled, including 24 managed with EF and 21 treated with VLP.

Ethical Approval

Ethical and scientific approval was obtained from the Scientific Committee of the Department of Orthopedics, Iraqi Board for Medical Specialization. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explanation of study objectives, operative techniques, and potential risks and benefits.

Participants

Eligible patients were adults aged 18–65 years with radiologically confirmed AO/OTA type C (C1–C3) unilateral distal radius fractures [4]. Exclusion criteria included pathological fractures, open fractures, polytrauma, previous ipsilateral wrist surgery, associated upper-limb fractures, delayed presentation ≥ 2 weeks, severe osteoporosis confirmed by DEXA, carpal tunnel syndrome, and neurological or cognitive impairment affecting reliable functional assessment.

Surgical Procedures

All procedures were performed under general anesthesia with standardized positioning and fluoroscopic guidance.

In the EF group, bridging external fixation was applied using the principle of ligamentotaxis, with Schanz pins inserted into the radial diaphysis and second or third metacarpal, followed by controlled distraction to restore alignment [15,16]. Supplemental K-wires were used when required.

In the VLP group, open reduction and internal fixation were performed via a standard volar (Henry) approach. A precontoured locking plate was positioned proximal to the watershed line, and subchondral locking screws were inserted to stabilize articular fragments [13,14].

Postoperative Care and Rehabilitation

Both groups received standardized postoperative care, including analgesia, antibiotic prophylaxis, and early finger mobilization. Immobilization was maintained for approximately two weeks. Structured physiotherapy commenced after confirmation of early union.

Outcome Measures

Functional outcome at three months was assessed using the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand (DASH) questionnaire, a validated 30-item patient-reported outcome measure (score 0–100). Secondary outcomes included wrist range of motion, grip strength (percentage of contralateral side), VAS pain score, radiographic parameters, complications, and return to work.

Statistical Analysis

Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation; categorical variables as frequency and percentage. Group comparisons were performed using Welch's t-test for continuous variables and χ^2 or Fisher's exact test for categorical data. Statistical analyses were conducted using R software (version 4.3.0), with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The ligamentotaxis and volar locked plate groups have broadly comparable baseline demographic characteristics, with a similar mean age (53.7 ± 9.4 vs. 51.1 ± 8.8 years, $p = 0.62$) and no statistically significant differences in sex distribution, affected side, or occupation type. The proportions of males and females were somewhat different between the groups (41.7% vs. 23.8% males and 58.3% vs. 76.2% females in the ligamentotaxis and volar plate groups, respectively), although this did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.10$). Hand dominance showed a statistically significant difference between groups, with right-hand dominance being more frequent in the volar locked plate group (95.2%) than in the ligamentotaxis group (75.0%), and left-hand dominance correspondingly less common (4.8% vs. 25.0%; $p = 0.026$). No significant differences were observed in occupation categories, with similar distributions of manual workers, office workers, housewives, and retired/unemployed individuals between the two groups ($p = 0.5$), as was seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics of Patients Treated with Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation for Type C Distal Radius Fractures

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
Age (years)	53.7 ± 9.4	51.1 ± 8.8	0.62
Sex			0.10
Male	10 (41.7%)	5 (23.8%)	
Female	14 (58.3%)	16 (76.2%)	
Affected side			0.2
Left	12 (50.0%)	7 (33.3%)	
Right	12 (50.0%)	14 (66.7%)	
Hand dominance			0.026
Left	6 (25.0%)	1 (4.8%)	
Right	18 (75.0%)	20 (95.2%)	
Occupation type			0.5
Manual worker	9 (37.5%)	6 (28.6%)	
Office/desk worker	6 (25.0%)	7 (33.3%)	
Housewife	6 (25.0%)	5 (23.8%)	
Retired/unemployed	3 (12.5%)	3 (14.3%)	
¹ Mean ± SD; n (%)			
² Welch Two Sample t-test; Pearson’s Chi-squared test; Fisher’s exact test			

With respect to smoking status, mechanism of injury, and AO fracture subtype, the ligamentotaxis and volar locked plate groups were largely similar. Non-smokers predominated in both groups (70.8% in the ligamentotaxis group vs. 52.4% in the volar plate group), while current smokers constituted 20.8% and 23.8%, and former smokers 8.3% and 23.8% of the respective groups; these differences were not statistically significant (p = 0.3). The mechanism of injury was

comparable, with Fall on outstretched hands being the most frequent cause (54.2% vs. 57.1% in ligamentotaxis and volar plate groups, respectively), and there was no significant difference between groups (p > 0.9). Similarly, the distribution of AO type C subtypes (C1, C2, C3) did not differ significantly between treatment arms (p = 0.86), indicating comparable fracture patterns at baseline, as was seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Smoking Status, Mechanism of Injury, and AO Fracture Subtype in Patients Treated with Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
Smoking status			0.3
Current	5 (20.8%)	5 (23.8%)	
Former	2 (8.3%)	5 (23.8%)	
Never	17 (70.8%)	11 (52.4%)	
Mechanism of injury			>0.9
Fall on outstretched hands	13 (54.2%)	12 (57.1%)	
Fall from height	5 (20.8%)	3 (14.3%)	
Road traffic accident	6 (25.0%)	6 (28.6%)	
AO fracture subtype			0.86
C1	9 (37.5%)	9 (42.9%)	
C2	13 (54.2%)	11 (52.4%)	
C3	2 (8.3%)	1 (4.8%)	
¹ n (%)			
² Pearson’s Chi-squared test; Fisher’s exact test			

The mean time from injury to surgery was also similar, at 4.3 ± 2.0 days for ligamentotaxis and 4.5 ± 2.3 days for volar plate fixation (p = 0.7). In contrast, the duration of surgery was significantly longer in the volar

locked plate group (88.3 ± 13.0 minutes) compared with the ligamentotaxis group (44.6 ± 6.9 minutes), with a highly significant difference (p < 0.001) as was seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Perioperative Characteristics and Comorbidities in Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
Time from injury to surgery (days)	4.3 ± 2.0	4.5 ± 2.3	0.7
Duration of surgery (minutes)	44.6 ± 6.9	88.3 ± 13.0	<0.001
¹ n (%); Mean ± SD			
² Fisher’s exact test; Pearson’s Chi-squared test; Welch Two Sample t-test			

Postoperative assessments at 3-month post-op showed several statistically significant differences between ligamentotaxis and volar locked plate fixation in terms of pain, radiographic alignment, and range of motion. The mean VAS pain score was lower in the volar locked plate group (2.4 ± 0.7) compared with the ligamentotaxis group (3.5 ± 0.9), with a highly significant difference (p < 0.001). Wrist flexion was similar

between groups (62.7 ± 8.1 vs. 62.6 ± 11.0 degrees, p > 0.9), whereas wrist extension (60.7 ± 9.0 vs. 54.0 ± 10.4 degrees, p = 0.011) and forearm supination (83.6 ± 9.2 vs. 77.1 ± 8.8 degrees, p = 0.006) were significantly greater in the volar locked plate group; forearm pronation did not differ significantly (p = 0.3), as was seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Pain Scores, Radiographic Parameters, and Wrist Range of Motion 3 Months after Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
VAS pain score	3.5 ± 0.9	2.4 ± 0.7	<0.001
Wrist flexion (degrees)	62.7 ± 8.1	62.6 ± 11.0	>0.9
Wrist extension (degrees)	54.0 ± 10.4	60.7 ± 9.0	0.011
Forearm pronation (degrees)	75.7 ± 10.9	78.7 ± 10.7	0.3
Forearm supination (degrees)	77.1 ± 8.8	83.6 ± 9.2	0.006
¹ n (%); Mean ± SD			
² Fisher’s exact test; Welch Two Sample t-test			

Figure 1: Error Bar Showing the VAS Pain Score and Wrist Extension 3 Months after Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

In terms of functional performance, patients treated with volar locked plate fixation demonstrated higher mean grip strength, expressed as a percentage of the contralateral side, compared with those managed by ligamentotaxis (81.4 ± 11.2% vs. 75.2 ± 9.4%), and this difference was statistically significant (p = 0.024). The

mean DASH score, reflecting self-reported upper limb disability, was slightly lower in the volar locked plate group (20.8 ± 5.3) than in the ligamentotaxis group (22.9 ± 7.6), but this difference did not reach statistical significance (p = 0.2) as was seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Grip Strength and Upper Limb Disability Scores 3 Months Following Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
Grip strength (% of contralateral side)	75.2 ± 9.4	81.4 ± 11.2	0.024
DASH score	22.9 ± 7.6	20.8 ± 5.3	0.2
¹ Mean ± SD			
² Welch Two Sample t-test			

Figure 2: Error Bar Showing Grip Strength 3 Months Following Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

The frequency of postoperative complications was low and comparable between ligamentotaxis and volar locked plate fixation, with similar proportions of superficial infection (8.3% vs. 9.5%, $p > 0.9$), deep infection (4.2% vs. 4.8%, $p > 0.9$), tendon complications (4.2% vs. 4.8%, $p > 0.9$), and complex regional pain syndrome (8.3% vs. 9.5%, $p > 0.9$). In contrast, the time to return to work was significantly shorter in the volar locked plate group, with a mean of 8.1 ± 2.0 weeks compared with 10.0 ± 3.0 weeks in the ligamentotaxis group ($p = 0.005$), representing the key statistically significant finding in this table, as was seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Postoperative Complications and Time to Return to Work after Ligamentotaxis Versus Volar Locked Plate Fixation

Characteristic	Ligamentotaxis N = 24 ¹	Volar locked plate N = 21 ¹	p-value ²
Post-operative complications			
Superficial infection	2 (8.3%)	2 (9.5%)	>0.9
Deep infection	1 (4.2%)	1 (4.8%)	>0.9
Tendon complication	1 (4.2%)	1 (4.8%)	>0.9
Complex regional pain syndrome (CRPS)	2 (8.3%)	2 (9.5%)	>0.9
Time to return to work (weeks)	10.0 ± 3.0	8.1 ± 2.0	0.005
¹ Mean ± SD; n (%)			
² Welch Two Sample t-test; Fisher's exact test			

Discussion

Functionally, the present study demonstrated significantly lower VAS pain scores, greater grip strength, and a shorter time to return to work in the volar locked plate (VLP) group compared with ligamentotaxis using external fixation (EF). Although DASH scores were numerically better with VLP, the between-group difference of approximately two points did not reach statistical significance, indicating broadly comparable overall upper-limb disability at three months. This pattern aligns with large meta-analyses by Fu et al. and Gou et al., which reported that VLP generally yields lower DASH and VAS scores than EF during the first postoperative year, particularly in early follow-up [17,18]. Gou et al. demonstrated significantly lower DASH scores at 3, 6, and 12 months with VLP, with minimal difference in final radiographic alignment [19], while Fu et al. similarly concluded that VLP offers superior early clinical and radiographic outcomes in unstable distal radius fractures [17]. Randomized

comparative trials further support this temporal pattern. Studies by Rozental et al., Williksen et al., Grewal et al., and Mellstrand Navarro et al. consistently showed superior early pain relief and functional recovery with VLP, whereas long-term DASH or QuickDASH outcomes frequently converged between techniques [20-23]. These findings suggest that the principal advantage of VLP lies in accelerated early recovery rather than substantial long-term reduction in global disability. Grip strength outcomes, however, remain heterogeneous in the literature. While the current study demonstrated significantly higher grip strength in the VLP group, meta-analyses by Egol et al. and trials by Gouk et al. have reported either no clinically important difference or slightly better early strength with EF [24,25]. Variability in fracture complexity, immobilization duration, rehabilitation protocols, and strength measurement methods likely contributes to these divergent findings [26]. Regarding range of motion (ROM), wrist extension and forearm

supination were significantly greater in the VLP group, whereas flexion and pronation were similar. Early superiority in extension and rotational planes has been attributed to the stability of internal fixation, allowing earlier mobilization [22]. Similar early ROM advantages with VLP were reported by Saving et al., though long-term differences diminished [27]. Subramanyam et al. likewise found comparable ROM at 12 months [28]. Despite better segmental outcomes, the absence of a significant DASH difference may reflect already low disability scores in both groups and the minimal clinically important difference of 10–15 points for DASH in distal radius fractures [29]. Complication rates were low and comparable, consistent with evidence that both techniques can be safely applied, though systematic reviews report VLP complication rates around 13–14% [30]. Economically, cost-utility analysis by Saving et al. suggested higher costs without long-term quality-of-life gain for VLP, raising questions about cost-effectiveness despite early functional benefits [27].

Conclusion

Both ligamentotaxis and volar locked plate fixation achieved satisfactory functional outcomes in AO type C distal radius fractures, with comparable complication rates. Volar locked plating resulted in significantly lower pain, better wrist extension and supination, stronger grip strength, and faster return to work. However, overall DASH scores were similar between groups, indicating comparable global upper-limb disability. Operative time was longer with volar plating, reflecting a trade-off between faster early recovery and increased surgical resource use.

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